

Multisensory Displays

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Deliverable Information Sheet

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Executive summary

In this report, we summarize the demonstrations of the different haptic displays designed by Inria and available to the GuestXR consortium to support social interactions in XR environments. A total of six demonstrations for four different haptic devices are presented. For more details, please refer to the video available here: <https://youtu.be/jtYVom5ixmc>

The video is also available on GuestXR's YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@GuestXR>

Table of contents

Deliverable Information Sheet.....	2
Executive summary	2
List of demonstrations.....	
Demonstration 1: Vibrations displays to increase persuasion when listening to other users.....	3
Demonstration 2: Vibrations displays to increase my persuasion when talking to other users	3
Demonstration 3: Thermal and vibrotactile feedback to augment persuasion and friendliness.....	4
Demonstration 4: Compression belt fostering empathy towards other users	4
Demonstration 5: Compression belt to enhance threat perception.....	4
Demonstration 6: Thermal suspenders to reduce cognitive stress.....	5
References	6

List of Demonstrations

Demonstration 1: Vibrations display to increase persuasion of other users

In this demonstration, the participants listen to other users and receive vibrations corresponding to their speeches to augment their persuasion (Saint-Aubert, 2023).

Demonstration 2: Vibrations display to increase my persuasion when talking to other users

In this demonstration, the participants talk to other users and receive vibrations corresponding to their own speech to augment their persuasion (Saint-Aubert, 2023).

Demonstration 3: Thermal and vibrotactile feedback to augment persuasion and friendliness

In this demonstration, the participants listen to other users and receive thermal feedback and vibrations corresponding to their speeches to augment their persuasion and friendliness (Hecquard, 2024).

Demonstration 4: Compression belt fostering empathy towards other participants

In this demonstration, the participants listen to a stressed user. They can feel the physiological state of the other participant changing with the stress thanks to the compression belt (Hecquard, 2023).

Demonstration 5: Compression belt to enhance threat perception

In this demonstration, the users observe characters approaching them and feel the compression belt tighten when the character is deemed to be threatening (Smekal).

Demonstration 6: Thermal suspenders to reduce cognitive stress

In this demonstration, the users perform a cognitive task of mathematical computation that stresses them. Cool thermal feedback is applied to their shoulders to help them relax (Philippe, 2024).

References

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